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AN EVALUATION OF AGENCY MODEL OF LIFE INSURANCE COMPANIES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The agency model has always been the most popular mode of selling insurance. The agency concept involves the recruitment of retired persons, housewives, self employed individuals or even students. The life insurance company provides professional training and gets them to target their acquaintances, friends and relatives and sell life insurance products. This strategy has always been used by life insurance companies because of the fact that in India, life insurance is still sold and not bought. The functioning of the agency model is always the biggest challenge to an insurance company since this group of people leaves the company without hesitation. Agents have by far been the most disloyal to the company especially in the case of private companies. In the recent past Bankassurance has gained a lot of popularity where in a person is forced to buy an insurance policy when he approaches the bank for a loan. However the success of a life insurance company is directly dependent on the training and development and maintaining of its agents. Insurance companies now have both individual and corporate agents selling policies on their behalf. India's private life insurance companies had examined the well-entrenched LIC's model of tied agents in detail and found it easy to replicate. They tweaked the overall branch-led operating model but retained the basic structure of brick and mortar branches and agency managers (or development officer in LIC parlance) on their payrolls i.e., the agency manager was an employee on fixed costs with some variable component. This made the agency in times where it is important to conserve capital and allocate capital to resources that will deliver sustainable returns; no insurer can remain rigid in their distribution or operating model.

This study evaluates the performance of private and public sector agents and analyses the need for insurance companies to move to other models for marketing life insurance.

Key words: Insurance, Agency Model, Performance, IRDA

Introduction

Life insurers have traditionally aligned themselves to models that are inherently conventional in its approach - individual agents, banks, corporate agents and insurance brokers instead of giving importance to either the customer or product segmentation. In fact while many insurers have built customer relationship databases, the data itself is not mined or tracked to increase the positive interactions with the customer. This has resulted in lower persistency levels (poor customer loyalty) and even resulted in customers avoiding face-to-face interactions with insurance agents. Persistency was long ignored by the insurance companies when the growth in new business premium was high. However, with the growth slowing down, focus on retention of policies has gained focus. Explosion of technology backed with the increase in internet and mobile telephony provides a low-cost opportunity as now life insurers can leverage some of the success of online banking and e-commerce to build an online product bouquet that engages the customer and enables him/her to buy. India's private life insurance companies had examined the well-entrenched LIC's model of tied agents in detail and found it easy to replicate. They tweaked the overall branch-led operating model but retained the basic structure of brick and mortar branches and agency managers (or development officer in LIC parlance) on their payrolls i.e., the agency manager was an employee on fixed costs with some variable component. This made the agency in times where it is important to conserve capital and allocate capital to resources that will deliver sustainable returns; no insurer can remain rigid in their distribution or operating model. Changing lifestyles and buying preferences will constantly dictate the future models of distribution. However, life insurers would also need to decide on the resources that need to be deployed to build these future models like Peer-to-peer (P2P) insurance or social insurance, Direct delivery model and Mobile-based insurance model. While the urban market today might be comfortable buying online insurance products, they might not resist the 'warm smile' of a life insurance agent. There are also successful models in other financial and non-financial services business that can be adapted to distribute life insurance products. It would be useful to examine some of them from an 'ideating' perspective. model a high-cost distribution model pushing the breakeven for these private life insurers.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the Indian Insurance market and make a comparative performance evaluation of the agency model in life insurance companies.

2. To compare the business achieved by life insurance companies through the agency model with the amount of expenditure incurred.

Methodology

This study is based on secondary data. Data required for the survey was collected from company financial statements published on IRDA website, various publications, articles, journals, and related sites.

Performance Evaluation of Agency Model of Insurance

The agency model has always been the most popular mode of selling insurance. The agency concept involves the recruitment of retired persons, housewives, self employed individuals or even students. The life insurance company provides professional training and gets them to target their acquaintances, friends and relatives and sell life insurance products. This strategy has always been used by life insurance companies because of the fact that in India, life insurance is still sold and not bought. The functioning of the agency model is always the biggest challenge to an insurance company since this group of people leaves the company without hesitation. Agents have by far been the most disloyal to the company especially in the case of private companies. In the recent past Bankassurance has gained a lot of popularity where in a person is forced to buy an insurance policy when he approaches the bank for a loan. However the success of a life insurance company is directly dependent on the training and development and maintaining of its agents. Insurance companies now have both individual and corporate agents selling policies on their behalf. The following table indicates the number of individual agents of various life insurance companies.

The below table shows the total number of agents of LIC and top private companies along with the average number of agents. The average number of agents in LIC 1235716 is almost the same as the total of all the agents of private sector companies put together. The Agency model is most popular as a brand name in LIC and it is quite common for agents of other private companies be taken for granted that any agent is a representative of the public sector LIC only. Among the private companies the highest average number of agents is of ICICI with an average of 233106 active agents. Bajaj Allianz has the second most average number of agents of 184052 followed by Reliance with an average of 158431 agents who are currently active. Most of the companies except SBI Life and Bajaj Allianz saw a massive drop in the number of agents in the year 2011-12. However the table shows that the number

of agents have been increasing and decreasing very erratically over the past seven years of the study.

Table 1.1: Table showing number of individual agents of life insurers

INSURER	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	Average
LIC	1052993	1103047	1193744	1344856	1402807	1337064	1278234	1172983	1235716
HDFC Standard	34887	79109	144714	207626	198879	136009	106244	77503	140710
ICICI Prudential	72383	234460	306354	299879	241830	190407	138883	147547	233106
SBI Life	8128	25356	40643	68993	65532	29628	86989	94138	59915
Reliance	19965	95620	184194	149613	195565	189433	150590	124038	158431
Bajaj Allianz	109141	216191	250239	204941	167741	18967	173146	148000	184052
Aviva	10974	29052	35307	30838	32728	23219	19126	17470	27531
Private	370846	890152	1326748	1592579	1575476	1302328	1080651	949774	1298365

The following graph depicts the number of agents of public and private companies.

Graph 1 Number of Agents

Corporate Agents

Apart of individual agents, Life insurance companies employ corporate agencies and banks to sell policies. The policies sold by corporate agents have however not been as many as those sold by individual agents. However this model is gaining more popularity in the recent days. The following table states the number of corporate agents of various life insurance companies.

Table 1.2: Table showing number of corporate agents of life insurance companies

INSURER	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	Average
LIC	74	226	345	415	510	295	240	207	330.28
HDFC	15	33	848	371	374	8	8	9	238
ICICI	7	17	46	47	22	15	14	11	25.57
SBI	8	27	23	94	127	100	73	83	76.42
Reliance	4	12	39	126	225	67	45	14	76
Bajaj	26	87	520	682	864	289	26	87	368.71
Aviva	3	5	21	17	15	11	246	210	75.42

The table reveals that in spite of the fact that LIC was in existence nearly 58 years, the concept of corporate agents was one of recent origin. Hence in this segment, the private companies too are very close in their average number of corporate agents. Among all life insurance companies, Bajaj Allianz has the highest average number of corporate agents with 369 followed by LIC with an average of 330 agents. ICICI has the least number of corporate agents with an average of only 26.

The following table depicts the growth in terms of percentage in the number of corporate agents of various life insurance companies.

The table below shows that the highest average growth rate 350% is that of AVIVA however, it is seen that the pattern of growth of corporate agents in AVIVA is abnormal and therefore

not a correct representation. HDFC also reports average growth rate of 350% but is highly erratic and cannot be considered as a true and genuine representation of growth of corporate agents. LIC, ICICI, SBI and Bajaj report a more realistic growth rate and it is seen that the growth of corporate agents is much higher in private companies than in LIC. This is indicative of a future trend among life insurance companies where in they will work towards forming more corporate partnerships and tie ups for the sale of insurance products.

Table 1.3: Table showing growth in Number of corporate agents in percentages

INSURER	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	Average
LIC	205.4054	52.65487	20.28986	22.89157	-42.1569	-18.6441	-13.75	32.38
HDFC	120	2469.697	-56.25	0.808625	-97.861	0	12.5	349.84
ICICI	142.8571	170.5882	2.173913	-53.1915	-31.8182	-6.66667	-21.4286	25.30
SBI	237.5	-14.8148	308.6957	35.10638	-21.2598	-27	13.69863	75.98
Reliance	200	225	223.0769	78.57143	-70.2222	-32.8358	-68.8889	79.24
Bajaj	234.6154	497.7011	31.15385	26.68622	-66.5509	-91.0035	234.6154	123.88
Aviva	66.66667	320	-19.0476	-11.7647	-26.6667	2136.364	-14.6341	350.18

Policies sold under the Agency Model

The following table shows the average number of policies sold by the agents of LIC and various private companies.

The table 1.4 depicts that the individual agents of LIC have been most successful in selling an average of 29 policies which is by far the highest among all insurance companies. Among the private companies, agents of SBI Life have been the most successful selling up to an average of 13 policies per agent. In the Corporate agent sector HDFC far out beats the other companies with a total of 56628 policies sold in the year 2012-13. The growth in this segment has been only in the last two financial years in the case of HDFC and also in the case of ICICI Prudential which is next in line in terms of policies sold by Corporate Agents.

The following graph depicts the number of policies sold by individual and corporate agents of private and public sector life insurance companies.

Table 1.4 Table showing the average number of policies sold by individual and Corporate Agents

INSURER		2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
LIC	Individual	28	28	26	27	29
	Corporate agents	2190	1606	1708	2194	2569
Aviva	Individual	7	3	3	3	3
	Corporate agents	1211	1667	3870	7067	5870
Bajaj Allianz	Individual	6	5	4	3	3
	Corporate agents	1824	1286	1247	1717	1042
HDFC Standard	Individual	4	3	3	3	4
	Corporate agents	428	704	1751	47211	56628
ICICI Prudential	Individual	4	3	3	2	2
	Corporate agents	7723	7413	13195	16328	28843
Reliance	Individual	4	5	4	4	3
	Corporate agents	7448	5840	6412	6072	6608
SBI Life	Individual	11	13	8	6	6
	Corporate agents	5659	4405	3118	3820	4610
Private total	Individual	6	4	4	3	3
	Corporate agents	1857	2289	1976	2533	5064

Graph 2: Number of policies sold by individual agents

Graph 3: Number of policies sold by Corporate Agents

The following table shows the percentage of policies sold by public and private sector life insurance agents individually and through Corporate agents.

Table 1.5: Table showing Average Number of Policies by Individual and Corporate Agents and percentage growth in the respective segments

INSURER		2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	Average
LIC	Individual	0	-7.14286	3.846154	7.407407	27.6
	Corporate agents	-26.6667	6.351183	28.45433	17.09207	2053.4
HDFC Standard	Individual	-25	0	0	33.33333	3.4
	Corporate agents	64.48598	148.7216	2596.231	19.94662	21344.4
ICICI Prudential	Individual	-25	0	-33.3333	0	2.8
	Corporate agents	-4.01398	77.99811	23.74384	76.64748	14700.4
SBI Life	Individual	18.18182	-38.4615	-25	0	8.8
	Corporate agents	-22.1594	-29.2168	22.51443	20.68063	4322.4
Reliance	Individual	25	-20	0	-25	4
	Corporate agents	-21.5897	9.794521	-5.30256	8.827404	6476
Bajaj Allianz	Individual	-16.6667	-20	-25	0	4.2
	Corporate agents	-29.4956	-3.03266	37.69046	-39.3128	1423.2
Aviva	Individual	-57.1429	0	0	0	3.8
	Corporate agents	37.65483	132.1536	82.60982	-16.9379	3937
Private total	Individual	-33.3333	0	-25	0	4
	Corporate agents	23.26333	-13.6741	28.18826	99.92104	2743.8

The average of LIC is 28% and in case of private sector the percentage in case of individual policies is a meagre 4%. However in case of Corporate agents, the private sector companies far out beat LIC.

Performance of Agents

The following table 1.6 depicts the policies written by agents of various life insurance companies. The agents of LIC have consistently been the highest sellers of policies right through the period. It was found that due to severe competition from the private sector life insurance companies, LIC reinvented itself, improved training and development of its employees and agents and also designed new products that were customer centric to affirm its position as highest policy seller in the industry. Over the period of eight years, the total growth in the number of policies in LIC was more than 9 crores. The average growth over the years has been about 1 crore policies.

Private companies are far behind in the number of policies sold with the total policies being only 2% of the policies sold by LIC alone in the year 2005-06. Growth in the whole private sector has been a little over 1,40,00,00,000 in terms of number of policies sold with the major growth being shown in Bajaj Allianz.

1.6: Table showing number of policies in thousands

INSURER	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
LIC	179564	189419	192428	210154	226058	240381	255845	270251
HDFC Standard	590	752	996	1244	1497	1598	1762	1938
ICICI Prudential	173	734	1037	1313	972	1090	1293	1502
SBI Life	352	411	420	489	579	789	1204	1724
Reliance	77	189	220	234	600	1939	2154	2327
Bajaj Allianz	395	511	540	721	941	1820	2283	2507
Aviva	34	51	48	62	62	152	254	317
Private	3545	4746	5740	7533	9007	12839	15430	17605

The following graph depicts the number of policies sold in thousands by insurance companies.

Graph 4 Number of policies sold

The following table depicts the percentage of growth in policies sold by LIC and other private companies. The table shows that the rate of growth in LIC has been more or less consistent with an average growth of about 6% throughout the period of eight years. However in the overall private sector, there has been an average growth rate of 26%. The

average growth rate of HDFC is 19%, ICICI Prudential has an average growth rate of a phenomenal 59% over the seven year period. SBI Life has average growth rate of 27%, Reliance of 81%, being the company with the highest growth rate, Bajaj Allianz has grown at 32% and Aviva has an average growth rate of 44%

Table 1.7: Table showing percentage growth in number of policies

INSURER	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
LIC	5.488294	1.588542	9.211757	7.567784	6.335985	6.433121	5.630753
HDFC Standard	27.45763	32.44681	24.8996	20.33762	6.746827	10.26283	9.988649
ICICI Prudential	324.2775	41.28065	26.61524	-25.9711	12.13992	18.62385	16.16396
SBI Life	16.76136	2.189781	16.42857	18.40491	36.26943	52.59823	43.18937
Reliance	145.4545	16.40212	6.363636	156.4103	223.1667	11.08819	8.031569
Bajaj Allianz	29.36709	5.675147	33.51852	30.51318	93.41126	25.43956	9.811651
Aviva	50	-5.88235	29.16667	0	145.1613	67.10526	24.80315
Private	33.8787	20.94395	31.23693	19.56724	42.54469	20.1807	14.09592

The amount of commission paid by LIC has increased by over 590 crores and the premium paid during the period has increased by over 50 crores. Private companies have shown a steep incline in the second years followed by a steady decline in the next years.

The following table depicts the percentage of Premium received and Agents' commission. Except for HDFC all companies have almost the same average rate of commission paid on premium received.

Table 1.8: Premium received and Agent Commission (Rupees in Lakhs)

INSURE R		2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
LIC	Agent commissio n	956,809.66	1,003,324.33	1,211,031.28	1,330,867.71	1,403,563.27	1,479,026.03
	Premium received	14,978,998.6 7	15,728,803.8 5	18,607,731.0 8	20,347,339.7 1	20,288,927.8 4	20,880,357.9 7
HDFC Standard	Agent commissio n	47,681.15	52,549.73	42,489.04	35,125.86	20,992.68	12,032.52
	Premium received	35,125.86	42,489.04	52,549.73	47,681.15	57,763.94	63,939.56
ICICI Prudentia 1	Agent commissio n	81,096.83	69,998.95	60,296.78	56,067.59	60,546.87	76,541.68
	Premium received	1,356,106.12	1,535,622.08	1,652,875.41	1,788,062.90	1,402,157.80	1,353,823.80
SBI Life	Agent commissio n	40,537.97	46,788.41	66,616.80	67,105.40	51,836.37	51,141.34
	Premium received	562,213.72	721,210.32	1,010,402.65	1,291,164.29	1,313,373.84	1,045,003.29
Reliance	Agent commissio n	27,577.89	59,690.88	62,785.49	51,480.21	39,803.37	32,616.18
	Premium received	322,543.89	493,253.89	660,489.62	657,114.64	549,761.92	404,539.33

The following table 1.9 depicts the sum assured by LIC and private sector life insurance companies. The total value of sum assured by LIC has increased by more than 18 lakh Crores. The total increase in sum assured by all private companies together is 6.29 lakh Crores. Among the private companies, SBI Life has shown the highest amount of sum assured and the growth over the past seven years amounted to more than 74, 000 Crores.

The following table shows the Sum assured by the life insurance companies

Table 1.9: Table showing sum assured in Crores

INSURER	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
LIC	1280159	1397568	1485380	1784880	2061034	2435396	2787732	3119331
HDFC Standard	11801	14253	16973	22251	29544	35376	48128	86110
ICICI Prudential	13438	15403	21644	28914	27347	36278	58660	77661
SBI Life	7254	9155	10997	14455	18018	29725	52245	81456
Reliance	1767	3339	4102	6069	8723	22050	30271	34735
Bajaj Allianz	10619	12554	12998	15195	19098	53055	46001	54302
Aviva	201	415	294	828	3146	10198	38757	60902
Private total	94205	116411	135496	177682	212483	344271	517060	723092

The following graph depicts the amount of sum assured

Graph 5: Amount of sum assured

The following table shows the percentage of growth in sum assured by all the life insurance companies

Table 1.10: Table showing Sum Assured in Crores – Percentage growth

INSURER	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	Average
LIC	9.171439	6.283201	20.16319	15.47185	18.1638	14.4673	11.89494	14
HDFC Standard	20.7779	19.0837	31.09645	32.77606	19.74005	36.04704	78.91872	34
ICICI Prudential	14.62271	40.51808	33.58899	-5.41952	32.65806	61.69579	32.39175	30
SBI Life	26.20623	20.12015	31.44494	24.64891	64.97391	75.76114	55.91157	43
Reliance	88.96435	22.85115	47.95222	43.73043	152.78	37.28345	14.74679	58
Bajaj Allianz	18.22205	3.536721	16.9026	25.68608	177.804	-13.2956	18.04526	35
Aviva	106.4677	-29.1566	181.6327	279.9517	224.1577	280.0451	57.13807	157
Private total	23.572	16.3945	31.1345	19.58611	62.02284	50.18982	39.84683	35

In the above table LIC shows an increase steadily at an average rate of 14% in the total sum assured. The private companies in total on the other hand have increased at an average rate of 35% in sum assured

Conclusion

In the last few years, growth was the primary agenda across competition segments including public sector, old private sector and new private sector general insurance players. Changes in the external environment would continue to present growth opportunities and insurance companies would be better equipped to exploit them based on market insights and internal capabilities developed over the period of time. In order to deliver on the shareholders' expectations, the companies will be driven to strike a balance between growth, profitability and risk as they go forward. This would entail marked changes in the business strategy and the same would be cascaded to operational decisions related to product design, pricing,

channel monitoring, and operational effectiveness. Companies with a one-dimensional focus on growth or on profitability would lose competitive power either due to strain on capital or due to insignificance of the scale. Either way, this would support the emerging trend of overall profitable growth for the industry. Such a scenario would also aid niche players to develop sustainable business models and co-exist with the large players adding to the depth and maturity of the industry.

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